

ECO BULK

A Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Products

The EcoBulk innovation project will enable greater resource efficiency in the **automotive, furniture and building** industries, with a focus on **new materials** combining plastics, fibres and wood. EcoBulk will rethink and refine the **design and manufacturing** of products to boost the **reuse** of products/parts as well as the **recycling** of materials.

COMPOSITE BULKY MATERIALS

... are difficult to recycle and usually end up being incinerated or land-filled. EcoBulk will show how some material fractions previously considered non-recyclable can be used and re-manufactured, totally transforming some of the current linear business models.

ECOBULK Outcomes:

Rethink

A Design Framework for product reuse and manufacturing leading to products that can be (re)manufactured with over 80% recycled material.

Reuse

Decision Support System for materials and process choices to increase direct product and part reuse, remanufacture and recycling by 65%.

Refine

Improved circular composite materials and processes developed to TRL7+.

Result

LCA of demonstration products showing resource reduction of at least 50%.

50m

Every year in the EU, 50m tonnes of bulky waste are disposed of. Approximately 60% of this waste is made of plastics, textiles and wood.

2.7b

Of 2.7bn tonnes of waste in 2010, only 40% was re-used. Of that fraction, 70% was mineral waste. This suggests that wood and plastics are lagging significantly behind their re-use potential.

\$95bn

The use of composites is growing and the global market for composite products is expected to reach \$95bn globally by 2020, according to a report by "Composites UK"

10m

Furniture waste accounts for over 10m tonnes out of the 253m tonnes of Municipal Solid Waste reported in Europe in 2011

CIRCULAR ECONOMY

A truly circular economy requires materials that can maintain equal levels of value both at the start and at the end of each life cycle. This is not just about the materials; it also requires an integrated approach to the design, manufacture, collection and treatment of products. Welcome to EcoBulk.

€600bn

A circular economy could mean savings of €600 billion for EU businesses, equivalent to 8% of their annual turnover

450m

According to the EU, a circular economy could reduce EU Carbon Emissions by 450 million tonnes by 2030

580k

The EU estimates a circular economy could create 580,000 jobs within the EU by 2030

10%

The EU has adopted a mandate to reach a maximum of 10% of municipal waste going to landfill - the current EU28 average is 30%

EcoBulk is a 4-year H2020 EU funded project, consisting of a consortium of 29 partners, representing manufacturers, designers, research institutions and industry associations.

Find out more:

ecobulk.eu

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